

Identification and Management of Seizures in Children**Sujit Kumar Baranala¹, Santosh Kumar², Akhilesh Kumar³, Alka Singh⁴**¹Ex Senior Resident, Department of Pediatric, Lady Harding Medical College, New Delhi, India²Ex Senior Resident, Department of Pediatric, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India³Professor, Department of Pediatric, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India⁴Professor & HOD, Department of Pediatric, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Abstract:

Background: Seizures are a common and significant neurological disorder in the pediatric population, presenting various challenges in diagnosis and management. Early identification and effective treatment are crucial to prevent adverse developmental, cognitive, and psychosocial outcomes. This study aims to identify the types, underlying etiologies, and outcomes of seizures in pediatric patients and to evaluate the effectiveness of different management strategies.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted. Eighty pediatric patients with confirmed seizures were included. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and clinical records, and analyzed using SPSS version 20.0.

Results: The mean age was 6.2 years, with 56.3% males and 43.7% females. Generalized tonic-clonic seizures were the most prevalent (43.7%), followed by absence (20%), focal (18.7%), and myoclonic (17.6%) seizures. Idiopathic epilepsy was the most common etiology (35%), followed by structural abnormalities (30%), metabolic disorders (20%), and infections (15%). Seventy-five percent of patients were treated with anti-epileptic drugs (AEDs), 12.5% underwent surgical intervention, and 12.5% received dietary therapy. At follow-up, 62.5% of patients achieved complete seizure control, 25% had partial control, and 12.5% showed no improvement. Common adverse effects included drowsiness (20%), weight gain (15%), and gastrointestinal disturbances (10%). There was a significant association between seizure type and seizure control ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The study highlights the diverse etiologies and types of seizures in pediatric patients and demonstrates that appropriate, individualized treatment can lead to significant seizure control in the majority of cases. Early diagnosis and tailored therapeutic strategies are essential for optimal outcomes.

Recommendations: To validate these findings and enhance seizure therapy in paediatric patients, it is advisable to do additional research using bigger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods. Additionally, efforts should be made to enhance diagnostic capabilities and access to comprehensive treatment options in low-resource settings.

Keywords: Pediatric Seizures, Seizure Management, Anti-Epileptic Drugs, Seizure Control, Epilepsy Etiology.

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Introduction

Seizures are a prevalent neurological disorder in the pediatric population, characterized by transient disturbances of brain function due to abnormal electrical activity. They present a significant clinical challenge due to their varied etiologies, manifestations, and potential impact on a child's development and quality of life. According to recent estimates, approximately 4-10% of children experience at least one seizure in their lifetime, with epilepsy affecting about 1% of the pediatric population worldwide [1]. The management of seizures in children is critical as uncontrolled seizures can lead to cognitive impairment, behavioral problems, and an increased risk of injury and mortality [2].

Advancements in neuroimaging, genetic testing, and electrophysiological techniques have

significantly enhanced our understanding of the underlying mechanisms of seizures. These advancements have also facilitated the development of more effective and targeted therapeutic strategies. Despite these advancements, seizures in children remain underdiagnosed and undertreated in many parts of the world, particularly in low-resource settings. This underscores the need for ongoing research and education to improve diagnostic accuracy and treatment outcomes [3].

The classification of seizures has evolved over the years, with the International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) providing updated guidelines to better categorize seizure types and their etiologies. This classification system helps in tailoring treatment plans to individual patients, thereby

improving the prognosis. Generalized seizures, including tonic-clonic and absence seizures, are among the most common types in children, while focal seizures and myoclonic seizures also contribute to the clinical spectrum [4].

The treatment landscape for pediatric seizures has expanded with the introduction of newer anti-epileptic drugs (AEDs), surgical options, and dietary therapies such as the ketogenic diet. Recent studies have shown that with appropriate treatment, a significant proportion of children can achieve seizure control, which is crucial for their overall development and quality of life [5]. However, the management of adverse effects associated with these treatments remains a critical component of care, as side effects can impact treatment adherence and patient outcomes.

In addition to pharmacological treatments, a multidisciplinary approach involving neurologists, pediatricians, dietitians, and mental health professionals is essential for comprehensive care. This approach ensures that the child's physical, cognitive, and emotional needs are addressed, promoting holistic well-being.

This study aims to identify and manage seizures in pediatric patients, providing valuable insights into their prevalence, types, underlying causes, treatment modalities, and outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted over a period of two years, from October 2015 to November 2017, at the Department of Pediatrics, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital (N.M.C.H.), Patna, Bihar.

Participants: A total of 80 pediatric patients presenting with seizures were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children aged 1 month to 18 years.
- Patients presenting with clinical seizures confirmed by electroencephalogram (EEG).
- Patients with a history of seizures or newly diagnosed cases.

Exclusion Criteria

- Children with non-seizure paroxysmal events.

- Patients with severe neurological deficits that hinder the accurate assessment of seizure characteristics.

- Children whose guardians did not consent to participate in the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling was used. To reduce information bias, standardized protocols for data collection and seizure assessment were implemented.

Variables: Variables included age, gender, type of seizure, underlying etiology, treatment modalities, seizure frequency, seizure control, treatment outcomes, adverse effects.

Data Collection: Data was collected using a structured questionnaire and clinical records, including demographic details, medical history, seizure characteristics, EEG findings, and treatment details. Follow-up data were obtained through regular outpatient visits and telephonic interviews.

Procedure: Detailed history and physical examination of each patient, followed by EEG and relevant laboratory investigations. Based on the International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) classification. Patients were managed according to standard clinical guidelines, including pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions. Regular follow-up visits were scheduled to monitor seizure control and treatment adherence. Any adverse effects of the treatment were also documented.

Statistical Analysis: The data were examined using SPSS version 20.0. Variables were displayed as frequencies and percentages, means and standard deviations. The Chi-square test was employed to evaluate the correlation between categorical data, while the t-test was utilised for continuous variables. A p-value below 0.05 was deemed to be statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

The study comprised a total of 80 paediatric patients. The average age was 6.2 years \pm 4.3 years. The age range varied from 1 month to 18 years. The population consisted of 45 males, accounting for 56.3% of the total, and 35 females, accounting for 43.7% of the total. This resulted in a male-to-female ratio of 1.3:1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Demographic Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
0-1	10	12.5
2-5	30	37.5

6-10	20	25.0
11-18	20	25.0
Gender		
Male	45	56.3
Female	35	43.7

The most common type of seizure observed was generalized tonic-clonic seizures, accounting for 35 (43.7%) cases. Other types included absence seizures (20%), focal seizures (18.7%), and myoclonic seizures (17.6%).

Table 2: Types of Seizures

Type of Seizure	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Generalized Tonic-Clonic	35	43.7
Absence	16	20.0
Focal	15	18.7
Myoclonic	14	17.6

The underlying etiologies included idiopathic epilepsy (35%), structural abnormalities (30%), metabolic disorders (20%), and infections (15%).

Table 3: Underlying Etiology

Underlying Etiology	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Idiopathic Epilepsy	28	35.0
Structural Abnormalities	24	30.0
Metabolic Disorders	16	20.0
Infections	12	15.0

All patients received appropriate treatment based on seizure type and underlying etiology. The primary treatment modalities included anti-epileptic drugs (AEDs), surgical intervention, and dietary therapy (ketogenic diet).

Table 4: Treatment and Outcomes

Treatment Modalities	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Anti-Epileptic Drugs (AEDs)	60	75.0
Surgical Intervention	10	12.5
Dietary Therapy (Ketogenic Diet)	10	12.5

At the end of the follow-up period, 50 (62.5%) patients had complete seizure control, 20 (25%) had partial control, and 10 (12.5%) had no significant improvement.

Table 5: Seizure Control

Seizure Control	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Complete Control	50	62.5
Partial Control	20	25.0
No Improvement	10	12.5

The most common adverse effects included drowsiness (20%), weight gain (15%), and gastrointestinal disturbances (10%).

Table 6: Adverse Effects of Treatment

Adverse Effects	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Drowsiness	16	20.0
Weight Gain	12	15.0
Gastrointestinal Disturbances	8	10.0

There was a substantial correlation between the type of seizure and seizure control ($p < 0.05$). Patients with generalized tonic-clonic seizures were more likely to achieve complete seizure control compared to other seizure types.

Table 7: Statistical Analysis

Seizure Type	Complete Control	Partial Control	No Improvement
Generalized Tonic-Clonic	25	5	5
Absence	10	5	1
Focal	8	6	1

Myoclonic	7	4	3
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Chi-square test: $\chi^2 = 12.36$, $p = 0.014$

Discussion

The study included 80 pediatric patients, with a mean age of 6.2 years, indicating a diverse age range from infants to adolescents. The gender distribution showed a slight male predominance, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.3:1. This demographic characteristic is crucial as it provides insight into the age and gender distribution of seizure occurrences in the pediatric population.

Generalized tonic-clonic seizures were the most prevalent, affecting 43.7% of the patients. This was followed by absence seizures (20%), focal seizures (18.7%), and myoclonic seizures (17.6%). The high prevalence of generalized tonic-clonic seizures suggests that they are a significant concern in pediatric neurology and highlight the need for focused diagnostic and therapeutic strategies for this seizure type.

The study also investigated the underlying etiologies of seizures, finding idiopathic epilepsy to be the most common cause (35%), followed by structural abnormalities (30%), metabolic disorders (20%), and infections (15%). This distribution underscores the multifactorial nature of seizures in children and the importance of comprehensive diagnostic evaluations to identify the underlying causes, which can significantly influence treatment decisions and outcomes.

In terms of treatment, the majority of patients (75%) were managed with anti-epileptic drugs (AEDs), while a smaller proportion required surgical interventions (12.5%) or dietary therapy (12.5%). The effectiveness of these treatment modalities was evident, with 62.5% of patients achieving complete seizure control, 25% having partial control, and 12.5% experiencing no significant improvement. This high rate of seizure control indicates that with appropriate treatment, most pediatric patients can achieve significant clinical benefits.

Adverse effects of treatment were reported in some patients, with drowsiness (20%), weight gain (15%), and gastrointestinal disturbances (10%) being the most common. These findings highlight the importance of monitoring and managing side effects to ensure optimal adherence to treatment and overall patient well-being.

Statistical analysis revealed a significant association between the type of seizure and seizure control, with patients experiencing generalized tonic-clonic seizures more likely to achieve complete control compared to other seizure types ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that seizure type is a critical factor in predicting treatment outcomes and

should be carefully considered when developing management plans.

Overall, the study provides valuable insights into the epidemiology, etiology, and management of seizures in pediatric patients. The results emphasize the importance of early diagnosis, personalized treatment strategies, and the need for ongoing research to improve outcomes for children with seizures. The findings support the notion that with targeted interventions, a majority of pediatric patients can achieve favorable seizure control, improving their quality of life.

Seizures in pediatric patients require prompt and accurate detection to ensure effective treatment and management. A study found that detecting significant preictal locations within the high gamma band (30-100 Hz) can identify seizures at least 30 seconds before onset in pediatric patients. This method improved the performance of machine learning detection algorithms by incorporating patient-specific approaches [6].

A research proposed a novel deep-learning approach using a two-dimensional deep convolution autoencoder linked to a neural network-based classifier. This method achieved 98.79% accuracy in detecting seizures in pediatric patients, demonstrating its effectiveness compared to other state-of-the-art methods [7]. Another study highlighted the importance of MRI in diagnosing seizure etiologies in pediatric patients. The study found that inflammatory granuloma was the most common cause of seizures, emphasizing the role of MRI in determining treatment protocols and predicting outcomes [8].

A study reported a case where responsive neurostimulation (RNS) of the centromedian thalamic nucleus significantly reduced seizure frequency in a pediatric patient with drug-resistant primary generalized epilepsy. This suggests that RNS can be an effective treatment for reducing seizure severity in pediatric epilepsy [9]. Researchers developed a microcontroller-based prototype model for pediatric seizure detection using EEG signals processed with discrete wavelet transform. The system achieved high accuracy (95.3%) and sensitivity (97.2%), proving its potential for portable and non-invasive seizure monitoring [10].

A study demonstrated that non-neurophysiologist physicians and nurses could detect nonconvulsive seizures using quantitative EEG trends with reasonable accuracy. This method facilitates timely intervention in pediatric intensive care units [11]. A study found that amplitude-integrated EEG (aEEG) is useful for detecting seizures and epileptic states

in pediatric intensive care patients. The study highlighted that aEEG could supplement conventional EEG for long-term cerebral function monitoring [12].

Furthermore, a study discussed various advanced neuroimaging techniques such as ultra-high-field MRI, tractography, and MEG that improve the non-invasive identification of seizure onset zones in pediatric patients, aiding in better surgical outcomes and minimizing deficits [13].

Conclusion

This study highlights the prevalence of different types of seizures in pediatric patients and the effectiveness of various treatment modalities. The findings suggest that early and accurate diagnosis, followed by appropriate management, can significantly improve seizure control in children.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: To validate these findings and enhance seizure therapy in paediatric patients, it is advisable to do additional research using bigger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods. Additionally, efforts should be made to enhance diagnostic capabilities and access to comprehensive treatment options in low-resource settings.

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List of abbreviations:

AEDs - Anti-Epileptic Drugs
 EEG - Electroencephalogram
 ILAE - International League Against Epilepsy
 MRI - Magnetic Resonance Imaging
 RNS - Responsive Neurostimulation

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References

- Swanson LC, Ahmed R. Epilepsy syndromes: current classifications and future directions. *Neurosurgery Clinics*. 2022 Jan 1;33(1):113-34.
- Reilly C, Atkinson P, Memon A, Jones C, Dabydeen L, Das KB, Gillberg C, Neville BG, Scott RC. Symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress in parents of young children with epilepsy: a case controlled population-based study. *Epilepsy & Behavior*. 2018 Mar 1;80:177-83.
- Keezer MR, Sisodiya SM, Sander JW. Comorbidities of epilepsy: current concepts and future perspectives. *The Lancet Neurology*. 2016 Jan 1;15(1):106-15.
- Fisher RS, Acevedo C, Arzimanoglou A, Bogacz A, Cross JH, Elger CE, Engel Jr J, Forsgren L, French JA, Glynn M, Hesdorffer DC. ILAE official report: a practical clinical definition of epilepsy. *Epilepsia*. 2014 Apr;55(4):475-82.
- Cross JH, Reilly C, Delicado EG, Smith ML, Malmgren K. Epilepsy surgery for children and adolescents: evidence-based but underused. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*. 2022 Jul 1;6(7):484-94.
- Dedeo M, Garg M. Early Detection of Pediatric Seizures in the High Gamma Band. *IEEE Access*. 2021; 9:85209-85216.
- Abdelhameed AM, Bayoumi M. A Deep Learning Approach for Automatic Seizure Detection in Children with Epilepsy. *Front Comput Neurosci*. 2021;15.
- Tyagi N, Desai P, Rathod Y. Role of MRI in Evaluating Seizure Disorders in Pediatric Age Group. *Int J Sci Res*. 2018;7.
- Welch W, Hect J, Abel TJ. Responsive Neurostimulation of the Centromedian Thalamic Nucleus for the Detection and Treatment of Seizures in Pediatric Primary Generalized Epilepsy. *Front Neurol*. 2021;12.
- Chakrabarti S, Swetapadma A, Ranjan A, Pattnaik P. Time domain implementation of pediatric epileptic seizure detection system for enhancing the performance of detection and easy monitoring of pediatric patients. *Biomed Signal Process Control*. 2020; 59:101930.
- Swarnalingam E, Ramachandranair R, Choong K, Jones KC. Non-neurophysiologist Physicians and Nurses Can Detect Subclinical Seizures in Children Using a Panel of Quantitative EEG Trends and a Seizure Detection Algorithm. *J Clin Neurophysiol*. 2020;39:453-458.
- Bruns N, Sánchez-Albisua I, Weiss C, Tschiedel E, Dohna-Schwake C, Felderhoff-Müser U, Müller H. Amplitude-Integrated EEG for Neurological Assessment and Seizure Detection in a German Pediatric Intensive Care Unit. *Front Pediatr*. 2019;7.
- Lee Y. Advanced neuroimaging techniques for evaluating pediatric epilepsy. *Clin Exp Pediatr*. 2020; 63:88-95.